

Novel isolates double the number of chemotrophic species and allow the first description of higher taxa in *Acidobacteria* subdivision 4

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The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession numbers for the 16S rRNA gene sequences of strains Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T, and Ac_28_D10^T are KP638489, KP638491, KP334257, and KF840371, respectively.

1 Abstract

2 Despite their high phylogenetic diversity and abundance in soils worldwide, *Acidobacteria*
3 remain an enigmatic bacterial phylum. Four novel *Acidobacteria* strains were isolated from
4 Namibian semiarid savannah soils using low-nutrient cultivation media and extended
5 incubation periods. 16S rRNA gene sequence analyses placed isolates within *Acidobacteria*
6 subdivision 4. Sequence identities with their closest relatives *Aridibacter famidurans* and
7 *Blastocatella fastidiosa* were $\leq 94.9\%$. The Gram-negative, non-motile, rod-shaped, aerobic,
8 and chemoorganotrophic bacteria grew at minimum doubling times of 5 to 14 h and formed
9 tiny white to pinkish colonies. Major polar lipids were diphosphatidylglycerol,
10 phosphatidylethanolamine, phosphatidylcholine, and phosphatidylglycerol. The major
11 isoprenoid quinone was MK-8. The major fatty acid methyl esters comprised *iso*-C_{15:0}, *iso*-
12 C_{15:1}H/C_{13:0} 3-OH, and C_{16:1} ω 7c/C_{16:1} ω 6c. Based on our polyphasic taxonomic
13 characterization, strain Ac_18_E7^T (=DSM 26557^T=LMG 28656^T) represents a novel species
14 and genus, *Tellurimicrobium multivorans* gen. nov., sp. nov.. The other strains constitute
15 three independent species of the novel genus *Stenotrophobacter* gen. nov.,
16 *Stenotrophobacter terrae* sp. nov. (Ac_28_D10^T=DSM 26560^T=LMG 28657^T), *S. roseus* sp.
17 nov. (Ac_15_C4^T=DSM 29891^T=LMG 28889^T), and *S. namibiensis* sp. nov.
18 (Ac_17_F2^T=DSM 29893^T=LMG 28890^T). These isolates double the number of established
19 species and permit the description of higher taxa of *Acidobacteria* subdivision 4. We propose
20 the family *Blastocatellaceae* fam. nov. to summarize the currently known oligotrophic, slightly
21 acidophilic to neutrophilic mesophiles from arid soils. The superordinated order
22 *Blastocatellales* ord. nov. and *Blastocatellia* classis nov. also include the terrestrial species
23 *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* and the anoxygenic photoheterotrophic species
24 *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum* from microbial mats.

25

26 **Keywords:** *Acidobacteria*, *Blastocatellaceae*, *Blastocatellales*, *Blastocatellia*, oligotrophic,
27 subdivision 4.

28

29 **Abbreviations:** DPG, diphosphatidylglycerol; DDH, DNA-DNA hybridization; FAMES, fatty
30 acids methyl esters; MK, menaquinone; ML, maximum likelihood; MP, maximum parsimony;
31 NJ, neighbor joining; PC; phosphatidylcholine; PE, phosphatidylethanolamine; PG,
32 phosphatidylglycerol; PGL, phosphoglycolipid; SD, subdivision; SE, soil extract; SSE, soil
33 solution equivalent; TLC, thin-layer chromatography.

34 About 60 of the 90 recognized bacterial phyla comprise only few or even no cultivated
35 representatives [2, 37]. Members of the phylum *Acidobacteria* represent a major fraction of
36 soil bacterial communities where they constitute up to 79% of all bacterial cells [22].
37 Whereas >70,000 different sequence types of *Acidobacteria* have been detected by culture-
38 independent molecular methods [3, 4, 20, 23, 26, 32, 34, 62], only 31 species have been
39 cultivated and validly described to date [41]. After the isolation and characterization of the
40 first representative *Acidobacterium capsulatum* [25] in 1991, the rate of description of novel
41 species has substantially increased over the past few years [9, 16, 19, 26, 50, 58, 60] due to
42 better insights into the specific adaptations of these bacteria [13, 15, 18, 26, 29, 36, 38, 40]
43 and subsequently improved cultivation methods [13, 16, 40]. However, the successful
44 isolation of novel *Acidobacteria* to date has been strongly biased toward a single subdivision.

45 The phylum *Acidobacteria* is divided into 26 subdivisions [3]. The majority of the presently
46 described species are affiliated with *Acidobacteria* subdivision 1 (21 species, including only
47 one species with name not yet validated “*Acidipila rosea*”). Additional species are known for
48 subdivisions 3 (two species), 4 (five species), 8 (three species) and 23 (one species).
49 “*Thermotomaculum hydrothermale*” has been described as a species of subdivision 10 [21],
50 but its name has not yet been validated. Subdivision 4 (SD 4) includes five validly described
51 species that are classified as four genera, namely *Blastocatella fastidiosa* [16], *Aridibacter*
52 *famidurans* and *A. kavangonensis* [19], *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* [9], and
53 *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum* [50]. Except for *C. thermophilum*, which has an
54 anoxygenic photoheterotrophic and microaerophilic metabolism, the other representatives of
55 SD 4 are characterized as rather slow-growing aerobic chemoorganoheterotrophs [9, 14, 16,
56 19], that use a narrow spectrum of carbon and energy sources, and are able to grow in low-
57 nutrient media [9, 16, 19].

58 In the present study, a high throughput cultivation approach was used to enrich and isolate
59 additional *Acidobacteria* of underrepresented subdivisions. Soil samples from Namibian
60 semiarid savannah soils located in Mashare (Kavango region; Supplementary Fig. 1) yielded
61 four novel strains designated Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T, and Ac_28_D10^T that
62 represent four additional novel *Acidobacteria* SD 4 species. Strain Ac_28_D10^T was isolated
63 from an agricultural old flood plain soil (17° 53' 32.4" S, 20° 11' 15.4" E), with slightly acid pH
64 (pH 6.6 and 5.7 measured in distilled water and in 2 mM CaCl₂, respectively). Strains
65 Ac_18_E7^T and Ac_15_C4^T were isolated from two different fallow soils (17° 55' 0.02" S, 20°
66 06' 18.7" E and 17° 53' 37.9" S, 20° 14' 50.7" E, respectively); the former being a Kalahari
67 sandy soil of slightly acidic pH (pH 6.2 in distilled water and 5.2 in 2 mM CaCl₂) and the latter
68 constituting an old flood plain soil of slightly basic pH (pH 8.2 in distilled water and 7.3 in 2
69 mM CaCl₂). All three soil samples were collected in spring 2011. The fourth strain,

70 Ac_17_F2^T originated from a riparian woodland soil (17° 53' 35.5" S, 20° 14' 57.5" E) with a
71 near-neutral pH (7.6 in distilled water and 7.2 in 10 mM CaCl₂) sampled in spring 2012.

72 According to their original pH, soil samples were dispersed in 10 mM HEPPS buffered at pH
73 8.0 (Ac_15_C4^T), in 10 mM HEPES buffered at pH 7.0 (Ac_17_F2^T) or in 10 mM MES
74 buffered at pH 6.0 (Ac_18_E7^T and Ac_28_D10^T) and total bacterial cell numbers were
75 determined after staining with SYBR Green I (Life Technologies). Cultivation experiments
76 were set up in sterile 96-well microtiter plates containing 180 µl of growth medium per well.
77 Each well was inoculated with 20 µl soil suspension containing 10 or 100 bacterial cells.
78 Strains Ac_28_D10^T and Ac_15_C4^T grew in medium Soil Solution Equivalent (SSE)/Cmix
79 buffered at pH 6.0 with MES and at pH 8.0 with HEPPS, respectively (Supplementary
80 Material and Methods). Strain Ac_18_E7^T was cultivated in medium SSE/HD 1:10 (=DSMZ
81 medium 1426) buffered at pH 6.0 (Supplementary Material and Methods). For cultivation of
82 strain Ac_17_F2^T, medium with Soil Extract (SE)/HD 1:10 buffered at pH 7.0 was employed
83 (Supplementary Material and Methods). After six weeks of incubation at 20 °C in the dark,
84 bacterial growth was detected by turbidity [19]. All positive enrichments were screened for
85 growth of *Acidobacteria* by group-specific diagnostic PCR using the primer pair Acido31f [4]
86 and 907r [28]. Cultures containing *Acidobacteria* were streaked on the same media used for
87 initial enrichment but solidified with 1.5% (w/v) agar. Strains were isolated by subsequent
88 streaking. Unless otherwise noted, all strains were routinely grown aerobically at 25 °C in
89 SSE/HD 1:10 buffered at pH 5.5 (strains Ac_18_E7^T and Ac_28_D10^T) or at pH 7.0 (strains
90 Ac_15_C4^T and Ac_17_F2^T). Data for reference strains were taken from literature since the
91 cultivation conditions in these previous studies are comparable (*Blastocatella fastidiosa* A2-
92 16^T, *Aridibacter famidurans* A22_HD_4H^T, and *A. kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T). The two
93 strains *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* K22^T and *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum* B^T
94 require specific growth conditions due to their different physiology [9, 16, 19, 50] and hence
95 cannot be tested in the media used for the former strains.

96 Phenotypic characterization was performed as described previously [16, 19]. Cells of all four
97 strains stained Gram-negative and had a similar morphology. They were short rod-shaped
98 with lengths of up to 2.5 µm and widths of up to 0.7 µm (Table 1). Spores or capsules were
99 not observed under any growth condition. All strains divided by binary fission. Whereas
100 strain Ac_18_E7^T formed small aggregates of up to 20 cells (Supplementary Fig. 2a), the
101 other three strains occurred as single cells or as pairs (Supplementary Fig. 2b-d). Unlike
102 *Blastocatella fastidiosa* A2-16^T, all strains isolated in the present study were non-motile and
103 formed only very small colonies that usually were less than 1 mm in diameter. After 1 week
104 of growth on solid SSE/HD 1:10 medium, strain Ac_18_E7^T produced white, circular, convex
105 colonies with regular edges that exhibited a bright pinkish color. Colonies of strains

106 Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, and Ac_28_D10^T were circular, convex with regular edges and pink
107 in color.

108 Ranges and optima of temperature and pH for growth were determined in duplicate or
109 triplicate under oxic conditions using liquid SSE/HD 1:10 medium as described previously
110 [19]. All strains were mesophiles with broad temperature optima and a broad temperature
111 growth range. None of them grew below 13.5°C or above 42.5°C (Table 1). The optima for
112 growth were found at slightly acidic pH (5.6-7.0). However, growth was detected at alkaline
113 (Ac_18_E7^T) or even highly alkaline (other strains) pH values (Table 1). With respect to both
114 parameters, the four strains resemble *Blastocatella* and *Aridibacter* spp., although showing a
115 more narrow range of optimum values. In contrast, *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* K22^T
116 and *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum* B^T are moderate thermophiles [9, 50]. Doubling
117 times under optimal conditions for strains Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T, and
118 Ac_28_D10^T were 5.1 h, 13.8 h, 12.0 h, and 11.9 h respectively (Table 1). With respect to
119 growth kinetics, only strain Ac_15_C4^T resembles the existing *Aridibacter* strains (doubling
120 times 5.5 to 6.1 h) whereas all other new isolates grew significantly slower than even *B.*
121 *fastidiosa* A2-16^T (doubling time 9.8 h).

122 The four novel strains exhibited an aerobic chemoorganotrophic metabolism. This type of
123 metabolism is shared by all members of SD 4 *Acidobacteria* except for the anoxygenic
124 photoheterotrophic strain *C. thermophilum* B^T [9, 50]. All strains except Ac_28_D10^T showed
125 catalase activity. Strains Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, and Ac_28_D10^T were also cytochrome-c
126 oxidase negative in contrast to Ac_18_E7^T and *P. methylaliphatogenes* K22^T. API 20NE and
127 API ZYM galleries (BioMérieux) were used following the instructions of the manufacturer and
128 examined after 48 h (API 20NE) or 4 h (API ZYM) of incubation. Like *B. fastidiosa* A2-16^T, *A.*
129 *famidurans* A22_HD_4H^T and *A. kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T, the four strains were unable to
130 reduce nitrate to nitrite, ferment glucose, hydrolyze urea, or anaerobically metabolize the
131 amino acid arginine with the release of ammonium. However, they showed a strong
132 hydrolysis of aesculin, except strain Ac_18_E7^T which only showed a weak response. Unlike
133 *B. fastidiosa* A2-16^T, none of them produced indol from the degradation of the amino acid
134 tryptophan and unlike both species of the genus *Aridibacter* they did not hydrolyze ortho-
135 nitrophenyl-β-galactoside (ONPG) by the enzyme β-galactosidase. Strains Ac_17_F2^T and
136 Ac_18_E7^T did not hydrolyze gelatin similar to *A. kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T (Table 1).
137 Strains Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T, and Ac_28_D10^T were characterized by
138 exoenzymatic activity towards phosphate-containing compounds (alkaline and acid
139 phosphatases and naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase), proteins (leucine arylamidase and
140 trypsin), lipids (esterase lipase C8), glycosides, and amino sugars (N-acetyl-β-
141 glucosaminidase) (Table 1). This is a property shared with the genera *Blastocatella*,

142 *Aridibacter*, and *Pyrinomonas* [9, 16, 19]. So far, no representative of SD 4 showed α -
143 galactosidase, β -galactosidase or α -fucosidase activity, however. The specific extracellular
144 enzymatic activities of the four novel isolates are further detailed in the respective species
145 descriptions below.

146 API 20NE galleries were not suitable for testing the utilization of carbon substrates. Possible
147 reasons are an inhibition of growth by a high concentration of nutrient in the commercial
148 media or the inability of the isolates to use the provided substrates. Therefore, the utilization
149 of individual carbon and energy sources by each strain was assessed using SSE as basal
150 medium containing per liter 10 mM buffer, 1 ml of the trace element solution SL-10, and 1 ml
151 of the vitamin solution (see Supplementary Material and Methods). The final concentration of
152 each substrate was described previously [19]. Substrates were scored as growth supporting
153 when an end-OD₆₆₀ (mean of two or three parallels) of 1.5 x the control value (= without the
154 addition of substrate) was reached. Optimal growth was defined as $\geq 75\%$ of highest growth
155 rate achieved. Weak growth was considered when the end-OD₆₆₀ of one or two of the
156 parallels excess the threshold (> 1.5 x the control value) and the other replicate showed an
157 end-OD₆₆₀ close to the threshold. Out of the 108 compounds tested, strain Ac_18_E7^T grew
158 on 29 different substrates, showing a weak response on eight of them (Table 1). In contrast,
159 the other three isolates were only able to use a narrow range of substrates. Strain
160 Ac_28_D10^T used six carbon sources of which two yielded only a weak growth response,
161 strain Ac_15_C4^T used seven substrates of which one only weakly supported growth, and
162 strain Ac_17_F2^T utilized 14 substrates of which seven yielded only weak growth. Strain
163 Ac_18_E7^T had a preference for sugars, organic acids and complex protein substrates such
164 as casamino acids, casein hydrolysate, peptone, and yeast extract. Strains Ac_15_C4^T,
165 Ac_17_F2^T, and Ac_28_D10^T preferentially used protocatechuate and complex protein
166 substrates. Similarly, the genera *Blastocatella*, *Aridibacter*, *Pyrinomonas*, and
167 *Chloracidobacterium* are characterized by a narrow range of growth substrates, preference
168 of protein-containing complex substrates, and the adaptation to relatively low nutrient
169 concentrations (Table 1).

170 The capacity of the four strains to degrade complex polymers was tested on solid basal SSE
171 medium (see above) amended with 0.005% (w/v) yeast extract and with the respective
172 substrates. After incubation, plates were stained with aqueous solutions of Lugol's iodine
173 (detection of starch; [8]), Congo red (detection of cellulose [51, 59], carboxymethyl cellulose
174 [51, 59], xylan [43, 51], or chitin [53]), ruthenium red (detection of pectin [10, 17]), ferric
175 chloride-potassium ferric cyanide (detection of lignin [48, 52]). To test laccase (phenol-
176 oxidase) activity, ABTS [2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid)] was used
177 [46, 52]. Only two positive results were obtained. Strain Ac_18_E7^T hydrolyzed starch and

178 strain Ac_28_D10^T showed laccase activity. Earlier positive results for starch and cellulose
179 degradation by *B. fastidiosa* A2-16^T [16, 19] were not confirmed in this novel test series.

180 For fatty acids analysis, the strains were cultivated in liquid SSE/HD 1:10 adjusted to
181 optimum pH values (pH 5.5 for Ac_18_E7^T and Ac_28_D10^T; pH 7.0 for Ac_15_C4^T and
182 Ac_17_F2^T) at 25 °C. Fatty acids were extracted, saponified and methylated according to
183 standard protocols (MIDI) [42], and individual fatty acids were identified using the Microbial
184 Identification System using the TSBA40 library (MIDI). The fatty acids profile of the four
185 novel strains included straight-chain, methyl- and/or hydroxyl-branched saturated and
186 monounsaturated fatty acids (Supplementary Table 1). While the four bacterial isolates
187 shared qualitatively similar fatty acids profiles with the other described species of
188 *Acidobacteria* SD 4, the relative abundances of individual fatty acids differed. The major fatty
189 acids of strain Ac_18_E7^T were C_{18:1} ω7c/C_{18:1} ω6c (22.2%), *iso*-C_{15:0} (16.3%), C_{16:1} ω7c/C_{16:1}
190 ω6c (10.6%), and *iso*-C_{15:1} H/C_{13:0} 3-OH (9.9%). In the case of strain Ac_28_D10^T only *iso*-
191 C_{15:0} (34.2%) and *iso*-C_{15:1} H/C_{13:0} 3-OH (24.9%) were found in higher amounts. Strain
192 Ac_15_C4^T was characterized by a high content of *iso*-C_{15:0} (31.1%), C_{16:1} ω7c/C_{16:1} ω6c
193 (12.9%), and *anteiso*-C_{15:0} (11.6%), while strain Ac_17_F2^T contained *iso*-C_{15:0} (30.2%), C_{16:1}
194 ω7c / C_{16:1} ω6c- (17.7%), and *iso*-C_{15:1} H/C_{13:0} 3-OH (11.4%). All representatives of SD 4
195 share as a common characteristic the presence of *iso*-C_{15:0} as a major fatty acid, but can be
196 easily differentiated mainly by their individual methyl-branched fatty acids (Supplementary
197 Table 1). The presence of *iso*-C_{16:0} as a major fatty acid is a diagnostic fatty acid of
198 *Blastocatella fastidiosa* A2-16^T [15]. High amounts of *iso*-C_{17:0} is a characteristic of
199 *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* K22^T [8]. On the other hand, the lack of *anteiso*-C_{15:0}
200 allows to differentiate the genus *Aridibacter* [19] from the genera *Tellurimicrobium* and
201 *Stenotrophobacter*, whereas the presence of C_{18:1} ω7c and/or C_{18:1} ω6c as well as *cyclo*-C_{19:0}
202 ω8c is an exclusive character of the genus *Tellurimicrobium*. *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum*
203 B^T is characterized by high amounts of *iso*-diabolic acid when total membrane lipid
204 composition is analyzed after acid hydrolysis of cell material [45, 50]. Isoprenoid quinones
205 were extracted from dried biomass with chloroform/methanol (2:1, v/v) [7] and analyzed via
206 HPLC [54]. The predominant respiratory quinone of all four strains was MK-8. Minor
207 amounts of MK-7 were also detected. Additionally, strain Ac_18_E7^T contained small
208 amounts of MK-9. This result is consistent with the quinone profile detected in most of the
209 other *Acidobacteria* SD 4 species where the major isoprenoid quinone is MK-8 and in some
210 cases (*Blastocatella* and *Aridibacter* spp.) also minor amounts of MK-7 occur [9, 16, 19].
211 Only in the case of *C. thermophilum* B^T the major isoprenoid quinone is MK-8(H₂) [50].
212 Subdivision 1 also shows MK-8 as predominant quinone, while SD 3 possesses MK-9 and

213 MK-10. Representatives of SD 8 contain MK-6 and MK-7, the sole isolates of SD 10 and SD
214 23 possess MK-7 and MK-8 or MK-10, respectively [16, 30, 58, 60].

215 The polar lipid composition of the four novel isolates was analyzed by two-dimensional TLC
216 [5, 55]. The major polar lipids detected were diphosphatidylglycerol (DPG),
217 phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), phosphatidylcholine (PC) and phosphatidylglycerol (PG). In
218 addition, strain Ac_18_E7^T produced an unidentified phosphoglycolipid (Supplementary Fig.
219 3). The genus *Aridibacter* shows the same polar lipids profile, whereas only PE and PC were
220 detected in high amounts in *B. fastidiosa* A2-16^T and *P. methylaliphatogenes* K22^T [19, 45].
221 *C. thermophilum* B^T contains the two unusual polar lipids phosphate
222 diacylglycerylhydroxymethyl-N,N,N-trimethyl-β-alanine (DGTA) and
223 phosphatidylmonomethylethanolamine (PME) in addition to PE and PC [50]. Polar lipid
224 profiles available for some species of SD 1, SD 3 and SD 23 are partially comparable to
225 those of the four novel SD4 isolates. Specifically, the major polar lipids of SD 3 are PC and
226 PE [27], whereas those characteristic of SD 23 are DPG, PG and PE [30]. Species of SD1
227 contain the major polar lipids DPG, PE, PG and/or other unknown phospholipids and
228 aminophospholipids depending on the individual strains [1, 11, 12, 31, 39, 58].

229 The molar G+C content of genomic DNA was analyzed using an HPLC protocol according to
230 Tamaoka and Komagata [49] and Mesbah et al. [33]. The DNA G+C content of strains
231 Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T, and Ac_28_D10^T was determined to be 56.8 mol%,
232 57.3 mol%, 59.4 mol%, and 58.5 mol%, respectively. These values are within the range
233 previously reported for other members of SD 4 (46.5 mol % to 61.3 mol %; Table 1), as well
234 as for the other *Acidobacteria* subdivisions (51.6 mol% to 63.2 mol%) [1, 16, 21, 30, 58, 60].

235 The almost full-length 16S rRNA genes of the four strains were amplified and sequenced
236 following the methodology detailed in the Supplementary Material and Methods. The
237 sequence lengths of Ac_15_C4^T (KP638489), Ac_17_F2^T (KP638491), Ac_18_E7^T
238 (KP334257), and Ac_28_D10^T (KF840371) were 1483 nt, 1483 nt, 1485 nt, and 1484 nt,
239 respectively. The additional 16S rRNA gene sequences used in this study were acquired
240 from public databases [35] and their accession numbers are provided with the phylogenetic
241 trees calculated with the NJ, MP and ML algorithms (Fig. 1, Supplementary Fig. 4). The
242 pairwise sequence similarities (%) between the strains are given in Supplementary Table 2.
243 According to the EzTaxon-e database [24], the closest type strains of Ac_18_E7^T,
244 Ac_28_D10^T, Ac_15_C4^T, and Ac_17_F2^T were *Aridibacter famidurans* (KF245634) sharing
245 94.9% 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity, *Blastocatella fastidiosa* (JQ309130; 93.4%
246 similarity), *Aridibacter famidurans* (KF245634; 93.5% similarity) and *Aridibacter famidurans*
247 (KF245634; 93.5% similarity), respectively. This result confirmed the phylogenetic placement

248 of these four strains within SD 4 of the phylum *Acidobacteria*. Independently of the tree
249 calculation algorithms used, the three strains Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, and Ac_28_D10^T
250 formed a well-defined monophyletic cluster sharing sequence similarity values between
251 99.1% and 96.3%, respectively. Strain Ac_18_E7^T formed a single, deeper branching,
252 lineage and shared a maximum similarity of 95.5% with the former three strains. This
253 arrangement was supported by high bootstrap values (Fig. 1). *A. famidurans* A22_HD_4H^T
254 and *A. kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T formed another well-defined monophyletic clade,
255 appearing *B. fastidiosa* A2-16^T as an external taxon. The sequence similarities between
256 these species and the novel isolates ranged between 93.6% and 94.9%. *P.*
257 *methylaliphatogenes* K22^T and *C. thermophilum* B^T formed an own cluster that was only
258 distantly related to the other SD 4 isolates. Strain Ac_28_D10^T shares a 16S rRNA gene
259 sequence similarity of < 97% with Ac_15_C4^T and Ac_17_F2^T and hence represents a
260 distinct species [47]. In contrast, the 16S rRNA gene similarity between Ac_15_C4^T and
261 Ac_17_F2^T was determined to be 99.1%. However, DNA-DNA hybridization analysis (see
262 Supplementary Material and Methods) yielded reciprocal re-association values of 33.2% and
263 28.8% for strains Ac_15_C4^T and Ac_17_F2^T which are well below the accepted threshold
264 value of 70% for species delineation, respectively [57]. Accordingly, despite their close
265 phylogenetic relationship the latter two strains represent different species.

266 Comparative protein analyses were carried out by Matrix-Assisted Laser-
267 Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) for the strains
268 Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T and Ac_28_D10^T, as well as for the type strains of the
269 species *Blastocatella fastidiosa* (DSM 25172^T), *Aridibacter famidurans* (DSM 26555^T), *A.*
270 *kavangonensis* (DSM 26558^T), and *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* (DSM 25857^T). For
271 biomass preparation, all strains were cultivated in liquid SSE/HD 1:10 at 25 °C for five days
272 except the thermophilic DSM 26557^T that had to be incubated in half-strength R2A broth
273 medium supplied with 0.2% (w/v) MgCl₂·6H₂O incubated at 60 °C for 5 days. Sample
274 preparation was carried out according to Protocol 3 of Schumann and Maier [44] and
275 instrumental conditions were used as described by Tóth *et al.* [56]. The resulting score
276 oriented dendrogram (average linkage, distance measure: correlation) was calculated using
277 the Biotyper software (Bruker Daltonics; version 3.1). Cluster analysis grouped the four novel
278 strains together, but clearly separated them from the described species of *Aridibacter*,
279 *Blastocatella* and *Pyrinomonas* (Supplementary Fig. 5). All novel isolates could clearly be
280 distinguished from each other based on their mass spectra. These results further
281 corroborate their description as novel distinct species.

282 So far, taxa above the genus level have not been described within SD 4 of the phylum
283 *Acidobacteria*. The four isolates described in the present study double the number of validly

284 described SD 4 species and thereby imply the first description of higher taxa in this
285 acidobacterial subdivision. The lowest interspecies 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity
286 value within SD 4 is 83.5% (Supplementary Table 2). As this similarity value lies above the
287 threshold level of 82.0% suggested for differentiation of bacterial orders [61], all established
288 genera are proposed as representatives of one single order *Blastocatellales* ord. nov. and
289 class *Blastocatellia* classis nov. (so far only known as subdivision 4). The proposed order
290 and class possess five nucleotide signatures in different regions of the 16S rRNA gene
291 (positions 371:390, 772:807, 929:1388, 1171, and 1313:1324 with respect to the *Escherichia*
292 *coli* numbering system [6]), which distinguish them from other *Acidobacteria* classes or
293 subdivisions with cultured representatives (Supplementary Table 3). The four novel isolates,
294 together with the genera *Blastocatella* and *Aridibacter* form a well-defined clade with a
295 minimum intracluster similarity of 93.0%, while the highest similarity value shared with the
296 genera *Pyrinomonas* and *Chloracidobacterium* is 85.0% (Supplementary Table 2).
297 Therefore, the former clade should be considered as an independent family [61],
298 *Blastocatellaceae* fam. nov. Sixteen nucleotide signatures are specific of this family which
299 distinguish it, partially or fully, from the genera *Pyrinomonas* and *Chloracidobacterium* as
300 well as from the other classes or subdivisions with cultured representatives (positions 69:99,
301 109, 319:334, 326, 327, 360, 381, 605:633, 725:732, 726:731, 784:798, 861:868, 895:904,
302 896:903, 1064:1192, and 1201 with respect to the *Escherichia coli* numbering system [6])
303 (Supplementary Table 3). To date, the family *Blastocatellaceae* fam. nov. comprises *K*-
304 strategists from nutrient poor soils with a strictly aerobic chemoorganotrophic live style that
305 prefer complex proteinaceous growth substrates. Further unifying characteristics are given in
306 the family description below. Based on our phylogenetic analysis, *Pyrinomonas*
307 *methylaliphatogenes* K22^T and *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum* B^T constitute two
308 additional deep phylogenetic branches within the *Blastocatellia*. It is therefore expected that
309 additional families will emerge once additional representatives of deeper phylogenetic
310 branches have been isolated. Based on the phenotypes of the two existing isolates, the
311 deeper branches might comprise mostly thermophilic taxa.

312 Therefore, collectively comparing the morphologic, metabolic, physiological,
313 chemotaxonomic, genetic, and phylogenetic properties of the four strains analysed in this
314 study, we conclude that strain Ac_18_E7^T represents a new species of a new genus for
315 which we propose the name *Tellurimicrobium multivorans* gen. nov., sp. nov. Strains
316 Ac_28_D10^T, Ac_15_C4^T, and Ac_17_F2^T represent three novel independent new species
317 constituting a novel genus for which we propose the names *Stenotrophobacter terrae* gen.
318 nov., sp. nov., *Stenotrophobacter roseus* sp. nov., and *Stenotrophobacter namibiensis* sp.
319 nov. In addition, we propose the formal description of the novel family *Blastocatellaceae* fam.

320 nov. to accommodate strains Ac_18_E7^T, Ac_28_D10^T, Ac_15_C4^T, and Ac_17_F2^T
321 together with the *Blastocatella* and *Aridibacter* spp. The novel order *Blastocatellales* ord.
322 nov. and the novel class *Blastocatellia* classis nov. accommodate the family
323 *Blastocatellaceae* fam. nov. together with the genera *Pyrinomonas* and
324 *Chloracidobacterium*.

325

326 **Description of *Tellurimicrobium* gen. nov.**

327 *Tellurimicrobium* [Tel.lu.ri.mi.cro'bi.um. L. fem. n. *tellus*, *telluris*, the ground, land, earth and
328 also a Roman goddess of the earth (*Tellus*); N.L. neut. n. *microbium* (from Gr. adj. *mikros*,
329 small; and Gr. masc. n. *bios*, life), a microbe; N.L. neut. n. *Tellurimicrobium* a microbe
330 isolated from the ground].

331 Gram-negative, non-spore-forming, non-capsule-forming, non-motile short rods. Cells divide
332 by binary fission. Aerobic chemoorganotroph unable to reduce nitrate and to ferment
333 glucose. Slightly acidophilic mesophilic. Positive for cytochrome-c oxidase and catalase.
334 Major FAMES include C_{18:1} ω7c/C_{18:1} ω6c, *iso*-C_{15:0}, C_{16:1} ω7c/C_{16:1} ω6c, and *iso*-C_{15:1} H / C_{13:0}
335 3-OH. Major polar lipids are diphosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylethanolamine,
336 phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylglycerol, and an unidentified phosphoglycolipid. The major
337 isoprenoid quinone is MK-8. The DNA G+C content of the type species is 59.4 mol%. The
338 type species is *Tellurimicrobium multivorans*.

339

340 **Description of *Tellurimicrobium multivorans* sp. nov.**

341 *Tellurimicrobium multivorans* (mul.ti.vo'rans. L. adj. *multus*, many; L. part. adj. *vorans*,
342 devouring; N. L. part. adj. *multivorans* devouring numerous kinds of substrates).

343 The description complies with the description of the genus and in addition includes the
344 following characteristics. Cells are short rods (0.8-2.3 μm long and 0.3-0.7 μm wide) that
345 occur as small aggregates. On solid SSE/HD 1:10 colonies are circular, convex with regular
346 edges, white with a bright pinkish hue in colour. Growth is observed at 13.5-42.5 °C
347 (optimum 34.0-37.0 °C) and at pH 4.7-8.4 (optimum pH 5.6-6.5). Doubling time under
348 optimal growth conditions is 12.0 h. Positive activity for alkaline and acid phosphatases,
349 naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase, leucine arylamidase, valine arylamidase, esterase lipase
350 C8, esterase C4, trypsin, chymotrypsin and N-acetyl-β-glucosaminidase, weak activity for
351 hydrolysis of aesculin and β-glucosidase, and no activity for cysteine arylamidase, lipase

352 C14, α -glucosidase, α -mannosidase, β -glucuronidase, α -galactosidase, β -galactosidase, α -
353 fucosidase, tryptophan deaminase, gelatinase, arginine dihydrolase, or urease. The
354 following sole carbon and energy sources are used for growth: arabinose, erythrose,
355 fucose, galactose, glucose, mannose, rhamnose, xylose, N-acetylglucosamine, arabitol,
356 mannitol, glutamate, glutamine, ascorbate, β -hydroxybutyrate, γ -hydroxybutyrate, citrate,
357 gluconate, 2-oxogluconate, 2-oxoglutarate, glyoxylate, lactate, pyruvate, succinate, glycerol,
358 casamino acids, casein hydrolysate, peptone, and yeast extract. With erythrose, fructose,
359 lyxose, aspartate, threonine, isocitrate, fumarate, and laevulinate, weak growth occurs. No
360 growth is observed with cellobiose, lactose, maltose, melezitose, raffinose, sorbose,
361 sucrose, trehalose, glucosamine, N-acetylgalactosamine, acetoin, adonitol, dulcitol, lyxitol,
362 myo-inositol, sorbitol, xylitol, alanine, arginine, asparagine, cysteine, glycine, histidine,
363 hydroxyproline, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, ornithine, phenylalanine, serine,
364 proline, tryptophan, tyrosine, valine, adipate, acetate, benzoate, trimethoxybenzoate,
365 butyrate, α -hydroxybutyrate, isobutyrate, caproate, caprylate, crotonate, formate,
366 glucuronate, glycolate, heptanoic acid, isovalerate, malate, maleic acid, malonate, nicotinic
367 acid, oxaloacetate, propionate, protocatechuate, shikimate, tartrate, 2-oxovalerate, butanol,
368 1,2-butandiol, 2,3-butandiol, ethanol, ethylene glycol, methanol, propanol, 1,2-propandiol,
369 fermented rumen extract, laminarin or Tween 80. Degrades starch but not cellulose,
370 carboxymethyl cellulose, xylan, chitin, pectin, lignin or ABTS.

371 The type strain is Ac_18_E7^T (=DSM 26557^T =LMG 28656^T), isolated from a Kalahari sandy
372 fallow soil in Mashare, Namibia (17° 55' 0.02" S, 20° 06' 18.7" E). The DNA G+C content of
373 the type strain is 59.4 mol%.

374

375 **Description of *Stenotrophobacter* gen. nov.**

376 ***Stenotrophobacter*** (Ste.no.tro.pho.bac' ter. Gr. adj. *stenos*, narrow; Gr. n. *trophos*, feeder,
377 one who feeds; N.L. masc. n. *bacter*, a rod; N.L. masc. n. *Stenotrophobacter* a rod feeding
378 on a few substrates).

379 Gram-negative, non-spore-forming, non-capsule-forming, non-motile short rods. Cells divide
380 by binary fission. Aerobic chemoorganotrophs unable to reduce nitrate and to ferment
381 glucose. Neutrophilic or slightly acidophilic mesophiles. Variable for catalase but negative for
382 cytochrome-*c* oxidase. Major fatty acids include *iso*-C_{15:0}, C_{16:1} ω 7*c*/C_{16:1} ω 6*c*, and *iso*-
383 C_{15:1}H/C_{13:0} 3-OH. Major polar lipids are diphosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylethanolamine,
384 phosphatidylcholine, and phosphatidylglycerol. The major isoprenoid quinone is MK-8. The
385 DNA G+C content is 56.8-59.4 mol%. The type species is *Stenotrophobacter terrae*.

386

387 **Description of *Stenotrophobacter terrae* sp. nov.**

388 *Stenotrophobacter terrae* (ter'rae. L. gen. n. *terrae* of the earth).

389 In addition to the characteristics that define the genus, the type strain has the following
390 characteristics. Cells are short rods (1.0-2.5 μm long and 0.4-0.7 μm wide) that occur as
391 single cells or in pairs. On solid medium colonies are circular, convex with regular edges,
392 shiny, and pink in color. Growth is observed at 16.6-40.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (optimum 28.6-34.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and at
393 pH 4.3-9.5 (optimum pH 5.5-7.9). Doubling time under optimal growth conditions is 11.9 h.
394 Displays activity of alkaline and acid phosphatases, naphtol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase, β -
395 glucosidase, N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase, and for hydrolysis of gelatin and aesculin. Weak
396 activity of leucine arylamidase, esterase lipase C8, trypsin, and α -chymotrypsin. Shows no
397 activity of valine arylamidase, cysteine arylamidase lipase C14, esterase C4, α -glucosidase,
398 α -mannosidase, α -galactosidase, β -galactosidase, α -fucosidase, β -glucuronidase, arginine
399 dihydrolase, tryptophan deaminase, or urease. The only substrates used for growth are
400 proline, protocatechuate, casamino acids and yeast extract, weak response is observed on
401 adonitol and casein hydrolysate. No growth occurs on arabinose, cellobiose, erythrose,
402 erythrulose, fructose, fucose, galactose, glucose, lactose, lyxose, maltose, mannose,
403 melezitose, raffinose, rhamnose, sorbose, sucrose, trehalose, xylose, glucosamine, N-
404 acetylglucosamine, N-acetylgalactosamine, acetoin, arabitol, dulcitol, lyxitol, mannitol, myo-
405 inositol, sorbitol, xylitol, alanine, arginine, asparagine, aspartate, cysteine, glutamate,
406 glutamine, glycine, histidine, hydroxy-proline, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine,
407 ornithine, phenylalanine, serine, threonine, tryptophan, tyrosine, valine, adipate, acetate,
408 ascorbate, benzoate, trimethoxybenzoate, butyrate, α -hydroxybutyrate, β -hydroxybutyrate,
409 γ -hydroxybutyrate, isobutyrate, caproate, caprylate, citrate, isocitrate, crotonate, formate,
410 fumarate, gluconate, 2-oxogluconate, glucuronate, 2-oxoglutarate, glycolate, glyoxylate,
411 heptanoic acid, isovalerate, laevulinate, lactate, malate, maleic acid, malonate, nicotinic acid,
412 oxaloacetate, propionate, pyruvate, shikimate, succinate, tartrate, 2-oxovalerate, butanol,
413 1,2-butandiol, 2,3-butandiol, ethanol, ethylene glycol, glycerol, methanol, propanol, 1,2-
414 propandiol, fermented rumen extract, laminarin, Tween 80, and peptone. Does not degrade
415 starch, cellulose, carboxymethyl cellulose, xylan, chitin, pectin, or lignin, but is positive for
416 laccase.

417 The type strain is Ac_28_D10^T (=DSM 26560^T =LMG 28657^T), isolated from an agricultural
418 old floodplain soil in Mashare, Namibia (17° 53' 32.4" S, 20° 11' 15.4" E). The DNA G+C
419 content of the type strain is 58.5 mol%.

420

421 **Description of *Stenotrophobacter roseus* sp. nov.**

422 *Stenotrophobacter roseus* (ro'se.us. L. masc. adj. *roseus* rose-coloured, pink)

423 In addition to the characteristics that define the genus, the type strain has the following
424 characteristics. Cells are short rods (0.9-2.0 μm long and 0.3-0.5 μm wide) that occur as
425 single cells or in pairs. On solid medium colonies are circular with regular edges and pink in
426 colour. Growth is observed at 15.5-41.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (optimum 34.5-41.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and at pH 5.0-9.5
427 (optimum pH 6.5-7.0). Doubling time under optimal growth conditions is 5.1 h. Shows activity
428 of alkaline and acid phosphatases, naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase, leucine arylamidase,
429 valine arylamidase, esterase lipase C8, trypsin, α -chymotrypsin, N-acetyl- β -
430 glucosaminidase, and hydrolysis of gelatin and aesculin. Weak activity of cysteine
431 arylamidase, β -glucosidase, and α -mannosidase are detected. Shows no activity of lipase
432 C14, esterase C4, α -glucosidase, α -galactosidase, β -galactosidase, α -fucosidase, β -
433 glucuronidase, arginine dihydrolase, tryptophan deaminase, or urease. Grows on heptanoic
434 acid, protocatechuate, casamino acids, casein hydrolysate, peptone, and yeast extract, but
435 not on arabinose, cellobiose, erythrose, erythrulose, fructose, fucose, galactose, glucose,
436 lactose, lyxose, maltose, mannose, melizitose, raffinose, rhamnose, sorbose, sucrose,
437 trehalose, xylose, glucosamine, N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylgalactosamine, acetoin,
438 arabitol, dulcitol, lyxitol, adonitol, mannitol, myo-inositol, sorbitol, xylitol, alanine, arginine,
439 asparagine, cysteine, glutamate, glutamine, glycine, histidine, hydroxy-proline, isoleucine,
440 leucine, lysine, methionine, ornithine, phenylalanine, serine, proline, threonine, tryptophan,
441 tyrosine, valine, adipate, acetate, ascorbate, benzoate, trimethoxybenzoate, butyrate, α -
442 hydroxybutyrate, β -hydroxybutyrate, γ -hydroxybutyrate, isobutyrate, caproate, caprylate,
443 citrate, isocitrate, crotonate, formate, fumarate, gluconate, 2-oxogluconate, glucuronate, 2-
444 oxoglutarate, glycolate, glyoxylate, isovalerate, laevulinate, lactate, malate, maleic acid,
445 malonate, nicotinic acid, oxaloacetate, propionate, pyruvate, shikimate, succinate, tartrate, 2-
446 oxovalerate, butanol, 1,2-butandiol, 2,3-butandiol, ethanol, ethylene glycol, glycerol,
447 methanol, propanol, 1,2-propandiol, fermented rumen extract, laminarin and Tween 80. A
448 weak response is observed on aspartate. Does not degrade starch, cellulose, carboxymethyl
449 cellulose, xylan, chitin, pectin, lignin, or ABTS. In addition to the major fatty acids common to
450 the genus *Stenotrophobacter*, it contains high amounts of *anteiso*-C_{15:0}.

451 The type strain is Ac_15_C4^T (=DSM 29891^T =LMG 28889^T), isolated from an old flood plain
452 fallow soil in Mashare, Namibia (17° 53' 37.9" S, 20° 14' 50.7" E). The DNA G+C content of
453 the type strain is 56.8 mol%.

454

455 **Description of *Stenotrophobacter namibiensis* sp. nov.**

456 *Stenotrophobacter namibiensis* (na.mi.bi.en'sis N.L. masc. adj. *namibiensis* of or belonging
457 to Namibia, the origin of the soil sample from which the organism was isolated).

458 In addition to the characteristics that define the genus, the type species has the following
459 characteristics. Cells are short rods (0.9-2.3 μm long and 0.4-0.6 μm wide) that occur as
460 single cells or in pairs. On solid medium colonies are circular with regular edges, shiny, and
461 pink in color. Growth is observed at 19.5-37.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (optimum 34.0-37.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and at pH 5.6-9.8
462 (optimum pH 6.1-6.5). Doubling time under optimal growth conditions is 13.8 h. Shows a
463 positive reaction for acid phosphatase, leucine arylamidase, valine arylamidase, esterase
464 lipase C8, trypsin, and hydrolysis of aesculin. Weak activity of alkaline phosphatase and
465 naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase are recorded. Shows no activity of cysteine arylamidase,
466 lipase C14, esterase C4, α -chymotrypsin, α -glucosidase, β -glucosidase, α -mannosidase, α -
467 galactosidase, β -galactosidase, α -fucosidase, β -glucuronidase, hydrolysis of gelatin,
468 arginine dihydrolase, tryptophan deaminase, or urease. Grows on tyrosine, isobutyrate,
469 protocatechuate, casamino acids, casein hydrolysate, peptone, and yeast extract, but not on
470 arabinose, cellobiose, erythrose, erythrulose, fructose, fucose, galactose, glucose, lactose,
471 lyxose, maltose, mannose, melizitose, raffinose, rhamnose, sorbose, sucrose, trehalose,
472 xylose, glucosamine, N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylgalactosamine, acetoin, arabitol,
473 dulcitol, lyxitol, adonitol, mannitol, myo-inositol, sorbitol, xylitol, alanine, arginine, asparagine,
474 cysteine, glutamine, glycine, histidine, hydroxy-proline, isoleucine, leucine, lysine,
475 methionine, ornithine, proline, aspartate, threonine, tryptophan, valine, adipate, acetate,
476 ascorbate, benzoate, trimethoxybenzoate, α -hydroxybutyrate, β -hydroxybutyrate, caproate,
477 caprylate, citrate, isocitrate, crotonate, fumarate, gluconate, 2-oxogluconate, glucuronate, 2-
478 oxoglutarate, glycolate, glyoxylate, isovalerate, heptanoic acid, laevulinate, lactate, malate,
479 maleic acid, malonate, nicotinic acid, oxaloacetate, propionate, pyruvate, shikimate,
480 succinate, tartrate, 2-oxovalerate, butanol, 1,2-butandiol, 2,3-butandiol, ethanol, ethylene
481 glycol, glycerol, methanol, propanol, 1,2-propandiol, laminarin, and Tween 80. Shows a
482 weak response with glutamate, phenylalanine, serine, butyrate, γ -hydroxybutyrate, formate,
483 and fermented rumen extract. Does not degrade starch, cellulose, carboxymethyl cellulose,
484 xylan, chitin, pectin, lignin or ABTS.

485 The type strain is Ac_17_F2^T (=DSM 29893^T =LMG 28890^T), isolated from a riparian
486 woodland soil in Mashare, Namibia (17° 53' 35.5" S, 20° 14' 57.5" E). The DNA G+C content
487 of the type strain is 57.3 mol%.

488

489 **Emended description of *Blastocatella fastidiosa* Foesel et al. 2013**

490 The description of the species *Blastocatella fastidiosa* is as given by Foesel et al. (2013) with
491 the following modifications. The ability to degrade starch or cellulose is not apparent.

492

493 **Description of *Blastocatellaceae* fam. nov.**

494 ***Blastocatellaceae*** (Blas.to.ca.tel.la.ce'ae. N.L. fem. n. *Blastocatella*, type genus of the
495 family; suff. -aceae, ending to denote a family; N.L. fem. pl. n. *Blastocatellaceae* the
496 *Blastocatella* family).

497 Gram-negative, non-spore-forming, and non-capsule-forming bacteria. Cells are spherical,
498 rod-shaped or pleomorphic, and divide by binary fission and/or budding. Aerobic
499 chemoorganotrophs, unable to reduce nitrate or ferment glucose. Oxidase and catalase
500 activities variable. Slightly acidophilic to neutrophilic mesophiles. Able to grow at low nutrient
501 concentrations. Preference for complex proteinaceous growth substrates while only few
502 complex carbohydrates are utilised. Mostly use a narrow range of substrates for growth.
503 Able to produce alkaline and acid phosphatases, naphtol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase, leucine
504 arylamidase, trypsin, esterase lipase C8, and N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase, but not α -
505 galactosidase, β -galactosidase or α -fucosidase. The major shared polar lipids are
506 phosphatidylcholine and phosphatidylethanolamine, but in some family members
507 diphosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylglycerol, and an unidentified phosphoglycolipid can be
508 also found in high amounts. The major isoprenoid quinone is MK-8. The major fatty acids
509 include *iso*-C_{15:0}, *anteiso*-C_{17:0}, *iso*-C_{15:1} H/C_{13:0} 3-OH, and C_{16:1} ω 7c/C_{16:1} ω 6c/*iso*-C_{15:0} 2-OH.
510 The family *Blastocatellaceae* contains the signature nucleotides 69:99 (U-A), 109 (A),
511 319:334 (A-U), 326 (A), 327 (U), 360 (G), 381 (A), 605:633 (U-U), 725:732 (G-C), 726:731
512 (U-A), 784:798 (G-C), 861:868 (G-U), 895:904 (C-G), 896:903 (A-U), 1064:1192 (G-U), and
513 1201 (A) (*Escherichia coli* reference gene [6]) which distinguish it, partially or fully, from the
514 genera *Pyrinomonas* and *Chloracidobacterium* as well as from the other *Acidobacteria*
515 classes or subdivisions with cultured representatives.

516 The family contains the genus *Blastocatella* Foesel et al. 2013, the genus *Aridibacter* Huber
517 et al. 2014, as well as the above defined novel genera *Tellurimicrobium* gen. nov. and
518 *Stenotrophobacter* gen. nov. The type genus is *Blastocatella* Foesel et al. 2013. Genomic
519 DNA G+C content ranges from 46.5 to 59.4 mol%.

520

521 **Description of *Blastocatellales* ord. nov.**

522 *Blastocatellales* (Blas.to.ca.tel.la'les. N.L. fem. n. *Blastocatella*, type genus of the order; suff.
523 -ales ending to denote an order; N.L. fem. pl. n. *Blastocatellales* the order of the genus
524 *Blastocatella*).

525 The delineation of the order is primarily determined based on phylogenetic analysis of 16S
526 rRNA gene sequences. In addition to the characteristics of the family *Blastocatellaceae*, the
527 order *Blastocatellales* thus also harbours moderately thermophilic and slightly alkaliphilic
528 bacteria or bacteria with an anoxygenic photoheterotrophic and microaerophilic metabolism.
529 In addition to the fatty acids given in the description of the *Blastocatellaceae*, *iso*-C_{17:0} and
530 *iso*-diabolic acid can be found in high amounts. MK-8(H₂) can be a major quinone.

531 Contains the family *Blastocatellaceae* and the genera *Pyrinomonas* Crowe *et al.* 2014 and
532 *Chloracidobacterium* Tank and Bryant 2015. The type genus is *Blastocatella* Foesel *et al.*
533 2014.

534 **Description of *Blastocatellia* classis nov.**

535 *Blastocatellia* (Blas.to.ca.tel'li.a. N.L. fem. n. *Blastocatella* type genus of the type order of the
536 class; suff. -ia ending to denote a class; N.L. neut. pl. n. *Blastocatellia* the class of the order
537 *Blastocatellales*).

538 The delineation of the class is primarily determined based on phylogenetic analysis of 16S
539 rRNA gene sequences and is equivalent to subdivision 4 of the phylum *Acidobacteria*
540 proposed by Barns *et al.* [3]. Signature nucleotides in the 16S rRNA gene sequence
541 (*Escherichia coli* reference gene [6]) differencing the class *Blastocatellia* from other
542 *Acidobacteria* classes or subdivisions with cultured representatives are: 371:390 (G-C),
543 772:807 (A-U), 929:1388 (A-U), 1171 (A), and 1313:1324 (U-A). The class currently
544 comprises the sole order *Blastocatellales* which also is the type order.

545

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549

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558 deposit of strains Ac_18_E7^T and Ac_28_D10^T is under the MTA of the NBRI (National
559 Botanical Research Institute, Namibia) of April 5, 2012. Isolation and deposit of strains
560 Ac_15_C4^T and Ac_17_F2^T is under the MTA of the NBRI of February 3, 2015. This work
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563

564

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749 855.

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752 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics among *Blastocatellia* species: 1, strain Ac_18_E7^T; 2, strain Ac_28_D10^T; 3, strain Ac_15_C4^T; 4, strain
753 Ac_17_F2^T; 5, *Aridibacter famidurans* A22_HD_4H^T [19]; 6, *Aridibacter kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T [19]; 7, *Blastocatella fastidiosa* A2-16^T [16];
754 8, *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* K22^T [9] and 9, *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum* B^T [50]. Cultivation conditions for phenotypic and
755 chemotaxonomic characterization were identical for the four novel strains and the reference strains, except for strains K22^T and B^T. +, positive;
756 –, negative; ND, not determined; W, weakly positive. AC, aerobic chemoorganotrophic; APM, anoxygenic photoheterotrophic and
757 microaerophilic; BF, binary fission.

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Cell shape	short rod	short rod	short rod	short rod	rod	rod	rod and sphere	rod	rod and sphere
Cell size (µm)	0.8-2.3x0.3-0.7	1.0-2.5x0.4-0.7	0.9-2.0x0.3-0.5	0.9-2.3x0.4-0.6	3.0-2.5x0.9	3.0-2.5x 0.7-0.6	12.0-0.8x 0.9-0.8	4-1 x 0.6-0.3	~2.5x1.0-0.8
Cell division	BF	BF	BF	BF	BF	BF	BF/ budding	BF	BF/ budding-like
Pigmentation	White (bright pinkish hue)	Pink	Pink	Pink	Yellow-pink	White (bright pinkish hue)	Orange-pink	White- semitransparent	Greenish-brown
Motility	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
Metabolism	AC	AC	AC	AC	AC	AC	AC	AC	APM
Doubling time (h)	12.0	11.9	5.1	13.8	5.5	6.1	9.8	ND	ND
Cytochrome-c oxidase	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	ND
Catalase	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND
Temperature for growth (°C)									
Range	14-43	17-40	16-41	20-37	15-44	12-47	14-40	50-69	44-58
Optimum	34-37	29-35	35-41	34-37	24-36	36-44	29-35	65	50-51
pH for growth									
Range	4.7-8.4	4.3-9.5	5.0-9.5	5.6-9.8	4.0-9.5	3.5-10.0	4.0-10.0	4.1-7.8	5.5-9.5
Optimum	5.6-6.5	6.0-8.0	6.5-7.0	6.1-6.5	5.5-9.0	5.5-8.0	5.0-7.5	6.5	7.0
Enzymatic activities (API 20NE)									
Indole production	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	ND	ND
Hydrolysis of Gelatin	-	+	+	-	W	-	+	ND	ND
β-Galactosidase	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	ND
Enzymatic activities (API ZYM)									
Valine arylamidase	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND
Esterase C4	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	ND
α-Chymotrypsin	+	W	+	-	W	+	-	-	ND
α-Glucosidase	-	-	-	-	W	-	-	-	ND
β-Glucosidase	W	+	W	-	+	+	-	+	ND
β-Glucuronidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	W	+	ND
Substrates for growth:									
Arabinose	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	ND
Erythrulose	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Fucose	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Galactose	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Glucose	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	W
Maltose	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	ND	ND
Mannose	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	W
Rhamnose	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	ND	ND
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	ND

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Xylose	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	ND
N-acetylglucosamine	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
N-acetylgalactosamine	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	ND	ND
Arabitol	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Mannitol	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Cysteine	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	+
Glutamate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Glutamine	+	-	-	-	-	W	ND	ND	ND
Methionine	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	+
Proline	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Tyrosine	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	ND	ND
Ascorbate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND
β-Hydroxybutyrate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
γ-Hydroxybutyrate	+	-	-	W	-	-	-	ND	ND
Isobutyrate	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	ND	ND
Citrate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Formate	-	-	-	W	-	-	-	+	-
Fumarate	W	-	-	-	-	+	-	ND	ND
Gluconate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
2-Oxogluconate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
2-Oxoglutarate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	+
Glyoxylate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-
Heptanoic acid	-	-	+	-	W	-	-	ND	ND
Isovalerate	W	-	-	-	-	+	-	ND	ND
Lactate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
Protocatechuate	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND	ND
Pyruvate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Succinate	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Glycerol	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
Laminarin	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	ND	ND
Casein hydrolysate	+	W	+	+	+	+	+	ND	ND
Peptone	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Hydrolysis of polymers									
Starch	+	-	-	-	-	-	- ^a	ND	ND
Cellulose	-	-	-	-	-	+	- ^a	ND	ND
ABTS (Laccase)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	ND	ND
DNA G+C content (mol%)	59.4	58.5	56.8	57.3	53.2	52.6	46.5	59.6	61.3

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759

^a Data obtained in this study

760 **Fig. 1.** Maximum Likelihood (ML) tree illustrating the phylogenetic position of
761 *Tellurimicrobium multivorans* Ac_18_E7^T, *Stenotrophobacter terrae* Ac_28_D10^T, *S. roseus*
762 Ac_15_C4^T, *S. namibiensis* Ac_17_F2^T and related members of the phylum *Acidobacteria*
763 based on almost full-length 16S rRNA gene sequences. The optimal evolutionary model of
764 nucleotide substitution applied is GTR+ I (p-inv= 0.2850) + G (gamma shape= 0.5290). Bar,
765 0.05 expected nucleotide substitution per site. *Armatimonas rosea* YO-36^T (AB529679),
766 *Fusobacterium nucleatum* NCTC 11326^T (X55403) and *Bacillus subtilis* DSM 10^T
767 (AJ276351) were used as outgroup. Only bootstrap values above 50% are indicated (1000
768 re-samplings) at branchings.

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Blastocatellia classis nov.
(=SD 4)

SD 3

Class *Acidobacteria*
(=SD 1)

Class *Holophagae*
(=SD 8)

SD 23

SD10

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**Novel isolates double the number of chemotrophic species and
allow the first description of higher taxa in *Acidobacteria*
subdivision 4**

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Running title: *Novel subgroup 4 Acidobacteria*

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25 **Supplementary material and methods**

26 **1. Culture media used in this study**

27 **a) Medium SSE/HD 1:10**

28 (=DSMZ medium 1426, <http://www.dsmz.de/>)

<i>Peptone</i>	0.50 g
<i>Yeast extract</i>	0.25 g
<i>Glucose</i>	0.10 g
<i>Buffer^a</i>	10 mM (final concentration)
<i>SSE (double concentrated)^b</i>	500 ml
<i>Distilled water</i>	500 ml
<i>Add to 1000 ml of medium after autoclaving:</i>	
<i>Trace Element Solution SL-10^c</i>	1.0 ml
<i>Vitamin Solution^d</i>	1.0 ml

29

30 **b) Medium SSE/Cmix**

<i>Buffer^a</i>	10 mM (final concentration)
<i>SSE (double concentrated)^b</i>	500 ml
<i>Distilled water</i>	500 ml
<i>Add to 1000 ml of medium after autoclaving:</i>	
<i>Mix of carbohydrates^e</i>	20 μ M each compound (final concentration)
<i>Mix of organic acids^f</i>	20 μ M each compound (final concentration)
<i>Mix of amino acids^g</i>	20 μ M each compound (final concentration)
<i>Aromatic compounds^h</i>	20 μ M each compound (final concentration)
<i>Trace Element Solution SL-10^c</i>	1.0 ml
<i>Vitamin Solution^d</i>	1.0 ml
<i>Inducers</i>	2 μ M each compound (final concentration)

31

32 **c) Medium SE/HD 1:10**

<i>Peptone</i>	0.50 g
<i>Yeast extract</i>	0.25 g
<i>Glucose</i>	0.10 g
<i>Buffer^a</i>	10 mM (final concentration)
<i>Soil extract mediumⁱ</i>	1000 ml
<i>Add to 1000 ml of medium after autoclaving:</i>	
<i>Trace Element Solution SL-10^c</i>	1.0 ml
<i>Vitamin Solution^d</i>	1.0 ml

33 ^a Buffered at pH 6.0 with MES, at pH 7.0 with HEPES, and at pH 8.0 with HEPPS

34

35 ^b SSE (Soil Solution Equivalent)- double concentrated:

CaCl ₂ x 2H ₂ O	0.2938 g
NH ₄ Cl	0.1069 g
MgCl ₂ x 6H ₂ O	0.2036 g
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.1983 g
MgSO ₄ x 7H ₂ O	0.7390 g
CaSO ₄ x 2H ₂ O	0.8606 g
Ca(NO ₃) ₂ x 4H ₂ O	0.2360 g
NaNO ₃	0.4240 g
KH ₂ PO ₄ (100 mM solution)	0.5000 ml
FeSO ₄ x 7H ₂ O	0.0111 g
K ₂ SO ₄	0.0870 g
add distilled water 1000 ml	

36

37 ^c Trace element solution SL-10:

HCl (25%; 7.7 M)	10 ml
FeCl ₂ x 4H ₂ O	1.50 g
ZnCl ₂	70.0 mg
MnCl ₂ x 4H ₂ O	100.0 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	6.0 mg
CoCl ₂ x 6H ₂ O	190.0 mg
CuCl ₂ x 2H ₂ O	2.0 mg
NiCl ₂ x 6H ₂ O	24.0 mg
Na ₂ MoO ₄ x 2H ₂ O	36.0 mg
Distilled water	990 ml

First dissolve FeCl₂ in HCl, then dilute with water, add and dissolve the other salts. Finally make up to 1000 ml.

38 ^d Vitamin solution:

Biotin	2.0 mg
Folic acid	2.0 mg
Pyridoxine-HCl	10.0 mg
Thiamine-HCl x 2H ₂ O	5.0 mg
Riboflavin	5.0 mg
Nicotinic acid	5.0 mg
D-Ca-pantothenate	5.0 mg
Vitamin B12	0.10 mg
p-Aminobenzoic acid	5.0 mg
Lipoic acid	5.0 mg
Distilled water	1000 ml

39

40 ^e Mix of carbohydrates: arabinose, fucose, β-gentiobiose glucose, rhamnose, trehalose,
41 xylose, N-acetyl-D-galactosamine, glucosamine and mannit.

42 ^f *Mix of organic acids: acetate, butyrate, citrate, formate, lactate, succinate, malate,*
43 *xaloacetate, 2-oxoglutarate, propionate, pyruvate and valerate.*

44 ^g *Mix of amino acids: alanine, arginine, cysteine, glutamine, glutamate, glycine, histidine,*
45 *lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, proline, serine, threonine, tryptophan, tyrosine,*
46 *asparagine, aspartate, leucine, isoleucine and valine.*

47 ^h *Aromatic compounds: sodium benzoate and sodium salicylate.*

48 ⁱ *Inducers: cyclic AMP, N-oxohexanoyl-DL-homoserine lactone and N-butyryl- DL-*
49 *homoserine lactone*

50 ^j *Soil extract medium (SE): The medium SE was prepared following the established*
51 *procedure (DSM medium 12; <http://www.dsmz.de/>), using a mixture of semiarid Namibian*
52 *savannah soils. After the autoclaving and centrifugation, the resulting supernatant was filtered*
53 *through a 0.22- μ m filter and then autoclaved a second time.*

54

55 **2. PCR amplification of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene and sequencing**

56 *The almost full-length 16S gene of strains Ac_15_C4^T, Ac_17_F2^T, Ac_18_E7^T and*
57 *Ac_28_D10^T was amplified directly by colony-PCR using primer pair 8f (5'-*
58 *AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') [7] and 1492r (5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'). PCR*
59 *mixtures included 2.0 μ l PCR buffer (10x), 0.8 μ l MgCl₂ (25 mM), BSA 0.4 μ l (20 mg/ml), 0.4*
60 *μ l dNTPs (10 mM each), 0.08 μ l each forward and reverse primers (50 pmol/ μ l), 0.08 μ l Dream*
61 *Taq DNA polymerase (5 U/ μ l Thermo Scientific) and 1.0 μ l DNA in a total volume of 20 μ l. The*
62 *thermal cycling program consisted of (i) 10 min at 94 °C; (ii) 32 cycles of 30 s at 94 °C, 30 s*
63 *at 56 °C and 1 min at 72 °C, and (iii) a final elongation step of 7 min at 72 °C. PCR products*
64 *were purified and sequenced using the above primer pairs and the internal primers 1055f*
65 *(5'-ATGGCTGTCGTCAGCT -3') [10] and 341r (5'-CTGCTGCCTCCCGTAGG-3') [12] and*
66 *by Sanger sequencing employing the AB 3730 DNA DNA analyzer (Applied Biosystems,*
67 *Foster City, CA) and the AmpliTaq FS Big Dye terminator cycle sequencing kit.*

68

69 **3. Phylogenetic analysis**

70 *Multiple sequence alignment was obtained using the Infernal aligner (INFERENCE of RNA*
71 *Alignment) version 1.1rc4 [13] as implemented in the Ribosomal Database Project (RDP)*
72 *release 11 [3]. Nucleotide sequence alignments were inspected visually to identify positions*
73 *of uncertain alignment to be corrected or omitted for further analysis. Phylogenetic analysis*
74 *was performed using the program PAUP* version 4.0b10 [15]. Neighbor-joining (NJ; with*
75 *Kimura's two-parameter evolutionary model), maximum-parsimony (MP; heuristic search*

76 option) and maximum-likelihood (ML) analyses were done. Since the lengths of the sequences
77 used were uneven, analyses were performed using a pairwise deletion method for gaps and
78 missing sites, using all available comparative data from each sequence pair. For ML, the
79 optimal evolutionary model of nucleotide substitution was estimated through the program
80 *jmodeltest2* [5] using the Akaike Information Criterion. Bootstrap analyses were performed
81 using 1000 replications.

82

83 **4. DNA-DNA hybridizations**

84 The established protocol for DNA-DNA hybridization [11] was used as modified by Huss et al.
85 [9] using a model Cary 100 Bio UV/Vis spectrophotometer equipped with a Peltier-
86 thermostatted 6 x 6 multicell changer and a temperature controller with in situ temperature
87 probe (Varian). Cells of strains *Ac_15_C4^T* and *Ac_17_F2^T* were disrupted in a Constant
88 Systems TS 0.75 kW (IUL Instruments) and DNA was purified from the crude lysate by
89 chromatography on hydroxyapatite [2]. DNA-DNA hybridization experiments were done in
90 duplicate in 2 X SSC + 5% formamide at 68 °C.

91

92 **Supplementary Tables**

93 **Supplementary Table 1.** Cellular fatty acid content of strains Ac_18_E7^T, Ac_28_D10^T,
 94 Ac_15_C4^T and Ac_17_F2^T compared with the type strains of the other species validly
 95 described within SD 4. Strains were cultured in liquid SSE/HD 1:10 buffered at pH 5.5
 96 (Ac_28_D10^T and Ac_18_E7^T) or pH 7.0 (Ac_15_C4^T and Ac_17_F2^T) for 10 days at 25 °C.
 97 Strains: 1, Ac_18_E7^T; 2, Ac_28_D10^T; 3, Ac_15_C4^T; 4, Ac_17_F2^T 5, *Aridibacter*
 98 *famidurans* A22_HD_4H^T [8]; 6, *Aridibacter kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T [8]; 7, *Blastocatella*
 99 *fastidiosa* A2-16^T [6]; 8, *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* K22^T [4]; 9, *Chloracidobacterium*
 100 *thermophilum* B^T [14, 16]. *Aridibacter famidurans* A22_HD_4H^T, *A. kavangonensis* Ac_23_E3^T
 101 and *Blastocatella fastidiosa* A2-16^T were characterized under the same cultivation conditions
 102 as for those strains introduced in this study. The other two reference strains could not be
 103 investigated under the same conditions as they require different growth conditions. Values are
 104 percentages of total fatty acids. –, not detectable; tr, trace amount (< 1%).

Fatty acid	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9 ^{b,c}
iso-C _{11:0}	tr	2.7	tr	tr	tr	tr	-	-	-
iso-C _{13:0}	tr	tr	2.8	3.0	4.1	3.5	1.0	-	-
iso-C _{13:0} 3-OH	1.8	tr	tr	tr	tr	-	tr	-	-
C _{14:0}	tr	-	-	-	tr	tr	-	-	2.9
C _{14:1} ω5c	tr	-	tr	tr	1.8	tr	tr	-	-
iso-C _{14:0} 3-OH	-	-	2.6	tr	-	-	tr	-	-
iso-C _{15:0}	16.3	34.2	31.1	30.2	35.1	38.0	5.0	40.8	35.6
anteiso-C _{15:0}	4.2	1.2	11.6	7.5	-	-	-	-	1.2
C _{16:0}	6.4	4.9	4.1	3.8	3.6	5.0	tr	1.8	4.1
iso-C _{16:0}	tr	tr	1.5	1.0	tr	1.9	15.7	-	4.6
iso-C _{16:1} H	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.6	-	-
anteiso-C _{17:0}	5.2	8.4	4.1	3.5	6.2	10.9	3.0	1.1	tr
iso-C _{17:0}	1.5	6.0	4.5	2.8	tr	1.7	1.3	33.8	2.5
iso-C _{17:0} 3-OH	1.4	-	1.9	1.9	1.8	1.5	1.2	-	-
anteiso A-C _{17:1}	tr	1.8	1.3	-	3.0	4.1	2.6	-	-
iso-C _{17:1} ω9c	-	-	1.5	3.4	tr	2.3	9.8	-	-
C _{18:0}	tr	tr	tr	tr	-	-	-	3.2	-
C _{18:1} ω9c	1.2	-	1.5	3.4	-	-	-	-	-
iso-C _{19:0}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.1	-
anteiso-C _{19:0}	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.2	-	-
cyclo-C _{19:0} ω8c	8.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C _{20:0}	tr	tr	tr	tr	1.1	tr	-	1.8	-
iso-C _{21:0}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.8	-
Summed feature 1 ^a	9.9	24.9	8.0	11.4	17.2	11.7	22.7	-	-
Summed feature 3a ^a	10.6	6.8	12.9	17.7	20.1	15.3	-	-	-
Summed feature 3b ^a	-	-	-	-	-	-	25.3	-	-
Summed feature 8 ^a	22.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Summed feature 9 ^a	4.9	5.3	8.8	7.4	-	-	-	-	-

105 ^a Summed feature represents a set of more than one fatty acid that could not be resolved by GLC
 106 with the MIDI system. Summed feature 1 contained iso-C_{15:1} H and/or C_{13:0} 3-OH; Summed feature
 107 3a contained C_{16:1} ω7c and/or C_{16:1} ω6c; Summed feature 3b contained C_{16:1} ω7c and/or iso-C_{15:0}

108 2-OH; Summed feature 8 contained C_{18:1} ω7c and/or C_{18:1} ω6c; Summed feature 9 contained C_{17:1}
109 ω9c and/or C_{16:0} 10-methyl.
110 ^b iso-diabolic acid represented 46.5% of the total fatty acids of strain BT.
111 ^c Total membrane lipid composition (in relative abundance %) after acid hydrolysis of cell material.
112 Data taken from Sinninghe et al. [14].
113

114 **Supplementary Table 2.** 16S rRNA gene pairwise sequence similarities (*p*-distances)
 115 between the type strains of species classified into the proposed class *Blastocatellia*.
 116 Strains: 1, strain *Ac_18_E7^T*; 2, *Ac_28_D10^T*; 3, *Ac_15_C4^T*; 4, *Ac_17_F2^T*; 5, *Aridibacter*
 117 *famidurans* *A22_HD_4H^T*; 6, *Aridibacter kavangonensis* *Ac_23_E3^T*; 7, *Blastocatella*
 118 *fastidiosa* *A2-16^T*; 8, *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes* *K22^T*; 9, *Chloracidobacterium*
 119 *thermophilum* *B^T*.

120

Strains	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1- <i>Ac_18_E7^T</i>	100								
2- <i>Ac_28_D10^T</i>	95.0	100							
3- <i>Ac_15_C4^T</i>	95.5	96.5	100						
4- <i>Ac_17_F2^T</i>	95.0	96.3	99.1	100					
5- <i>A22_HD_4H^T</i>	94.9	93.4	93.5	93.5	100				
6- <i>Ac_23_E3^T</i>	94.5	93.2	93.0	93.0	97.6	100			
7- <i>A2-16^T</i>	93.5	93.4	93.1	93.6	93.3	93.4	100		
8- <i>K22^T</i>	84.9	84.2	84.9	84.6	83.9	84.1	85.0	100	
9- <i>B^T</i>	85.0	84.2	84.9	84.7	83.8	84.5	83.5	87.6	100

121

122 **Supplementary Table 3.** 16S rRNA gene nucleotide signatures used for the differentiation of
123 the family Blastocatellaceae fam. nov., order Blastocatellales ord. nov., and class
124 Blastocatellia classis nov.. 1, family Blastocatellaceae; 2, *Pyrinomonas methylaliphatogenes*
125 *K22^T*; 3, *Chloracidobacterium thermophilum B^T*; 4, class Acidobacteriia (=SD 1); 5, SD 3; 6,
126 class Holophagae (=SD 8); 7, SD 10; 8, SD 23. Nucleotide positions refer to the *E. coli* 16S
127 rRNA reference gene implemented in ARB/SILVA (numbering according to Brosius et al. [1]).
128 Nucleotide signatures are highlighted in bold which allow to differentiate the order
129 Blastocatellales and class Blastocatellia from other Acidobacteria classes or subdivisions with
130 cultured representatives. Signatures are written in regular which distinguish the family
131 Blastocatellaceae, partially or fully, from the genera *Pyrinomonas* and *Chloracidobacterium*
132 as well as from the other classes or subdivisions with cultured representatives.
133

Position	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
69:99	U-A	G-A	G-A	G-A	G-A	G-U/C	G-A	G-C
109	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	A
319:334	A-U	G-C						
326	A	C	A	A	A	G	G	G
327	U	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
360	G	G	A	G	G	G	G	G
371:390	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-C	A-U	G-C	A-U	G-C
381	A	C	A	A	A	A	C	A
605:633	U-U	U-C	U-G	U-G	U-G	U-G	U-G	U-G
725:732	G-C	G-C	A-U	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-C
726:731	U-A	C-G	C-G	C-G	U-A	C-G	A-U	C-G
772:807	A-U	A-U	A-U	A-U	U-A	U-A	U-A	U-A
784:798	G-C	A-U	G-C	A-U	A-U	A-U	A-U	A-U
861:868	G-U	G-C						
895:904	C-G	G-C	A-U	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-C
896:903	A-U	U-A	C-G	U-G	U-G	U-G	U-G	U-G
929:1388	A-U	A-U	A-U	G-C	G-C	G-C	A-U	G-C
1064:1192	G-U	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-C	G-U/C	G-C	G-C
1171	A	A	A	C	G	C	C	A
1201	A	C	C	C	A/C	C	C	A
1313:1324	U-A	U-A	U-A	U-A	G-C	U-A	G-C	U-A

134
135
136

137 **Supplementary Figures**

138

139 **Supplementary Fig. 1.** *Map of the sampling site at Mashare village (red dot) in the Mashare*
140 *constituency (yellow area), within the Kavango region (yellow and gray areas), Northern*
141 *Namibia.*

142

143 **Supplementary Fig. 2.** Phase-contrast photomicrographs of strains *Ac_18_E7^T* (a),
144 *Ac_28_D10^T*(b), *Ac_15_C4^T*(c) , and *Ac_17_F2T* (d) grown under optimal conditions. Cells
145 were immobilized on agarose-covered slides (1% w/v) and images were taken with a Zeiss
146 Axio microscope at 100x magnification. Bars, 5 μ m.

147

148

149 **Supplementary Fig. 3.** Polar lipid profiles of strains *Ac_18_E7^T*, *Ac_28_D10^T*, *Ac_15_C4^T*,
150 and *Ac_17_F2^T*, after two-dimensional TLC (thin-layer chromatography) and detection with
151 molybdatophosphoric acid. To facilitate comparison only major polar lipids are labeled.

152

153 Abbreviations: DPG, diphosphatidylglycerol; PE,
154 phosphatidylethanolamine; PC, phosphatidylcholine; PG,
155 phosphatidylglycerol; PGL, unidentified phosphoglycerolipid.

156

157 **Supplementary Fig. 4.** Maximum Parsimony (MP) (a) and Neighbor-Joining (NJ) (b) trees
 158 illustrating the phylogenetic position of *Tellurimicrobium multivorans* Ac_18_E7^T,
 159 *Stenotrophobacter terrae* Ac_28_D10^T, *S. roseus* Ac_15_C4^T, *S. namibiensis* Ac_17_F2^T and
 160 related members of the phylum Acidobacteria based on almost full-length 16S rRNA gene
 161 sequences. For NJ tree, the evolutionary model K2P is applied. Bars, (a) estimated
 162 substitution per 50 bases positions and (b) 0.05 expected nucleotide substitution per site.
 163 *Armatimonas rosea* YO-36^T (AB529679), *Fusobacterium nucleatum* NCTC 11326^T (X55403)
 164 and *Bacillus subtilis* DSM 10^T (AJ276351) were used as outgroups. Only bootstrap values
 165 above 50% are indicated (1000 resamplings) at branchings.

b)

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169

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171

172 **Supplementary Fig. 5.** Score-oriented dendrogram generated by the MALDI-BioTyper
173 software (version 3.1, Bruker Daltonics) showing the similarity of MALDI-TOF mass spectra of
174 cell extracts of strains *Ac_18_E7^T*, *Ac_28_D10^T*, *Ac_15_C4*, *Ac_17_F2^T*, *Blastocatella*
175 *fastidiosa* DSM 25172^T, *Aridibacter famidurans* DSM 26555^T, *A. kavangonensis* DSM 26558^T,
176 and *Pyrinomonas methylaliphathogenes* DSM 28857^T. All spectra were obtained in this study.
177 Distances are displayed in relative units.

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